

PROFESSIONALISM AND FUNCTIONAL TEACHER EDUCATION IN NIGERIA: ISSUES OF QUALITY ASSURANCE AND TEACHER PERFORMANCE STANDARD

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Abstract

Teachers are regarded as custodians and transmitters of knowledge that inspires functionalities and keeps the society going. Their training or upbringing within teacher training is a reflection of their professional callings. It is in the light of this that this paper highlights teaching profession and functional teacher education, focusing on the goals of teacher education, the criteria of profession vis-à-vis teaching profession in Nigeria and the inherent contradiction of professionalism and teacher education. Recommendations are made as to strengthen professionalism and functional teacher education in Nigeria.

Keywords: Professionalism, Function teachers, Quality assurance.

Introduction

Professionalism as a concept stems from the word "profession" which could be explained via three perspectives: the generic, the ideological and the specialist. Generically it means an economic field of activity requiring academic preparation above the high school level. Ideologically, it is understood as a pivot for bargaining position in an occupation's effort to specialist perspective it refers to a body of economic activity that provides specialized activities based on acquisition of specialized knowledge and skills by members who subscribe to a recognized regulatory body's code and ethics governing the practitioners as well as control or admission of new members

(Okunloye: 2004).

In another realm, profession can be defined as a calling that requires acquisition of specialized knowledge which often involves long and intensive academic preparation. It is also explained by Salami (2009) as an occupation based upon specialized intellectual study and training, the purpose of which is to supply skilled service or advice to others for a definite sum of money.

The fore-going postulates that professionalism implies formalities that are undertaken to produce people devoted to a calling, a job, an occupation, from where they are rewarded via cash payments for services rendered. In other words, professionalism entails fulfillment of certain criteria or characteristics which Okunloye (2004) listed as:-

- * **Specialized training:** Before a person could qualify to practice as a professional in any field of human endeavour he or she must undergo a specialized training course of high academic and professional standard in a recognized institution.
- * **Standard for Admission into Membership of Professional Body:** New entrants into a profession must satisfy minimum requirements or qualifications before been allowed to practice i.e must be adjudged worthy and capable to become a member by being licensed to perform or render required services.
- * **Membership of a Recognized Professional Body:** A practitioner of a trade or occupation must of necessity belong or be duly registered with a professional body that closely knit members with high quality standards in line with current realities.
- * **Internship programme:** The period of training would allow for a period of internship. That is meant for a time of socialization into the professional practice .
- * **Code of conduct:** There must exist an observance of code of conduct or professional ethics. This is meant to serve as measures to maintain

standards, and an effective machinery to enforce the code of conduct.)

* **Remuneration and God condition of service:** Another criterion relates to prompt payments of salaries that compares favourably to salaries of colleagues in other fields of human endeavour. This is coupled with reasonable standard of living for the practitioner and his immediate family members

* **In service/ on the Job Training :** As we live in a changing world, certain dynamics should be put into cognizance which gives room for on the job training and re- training as to always up date practitioners on various innovations, techniques and use of modern technologies relevant to their calling.

* **Availability and use of Tools:** this entails the fact that practitioners must not only possess knowledge and skills, but must also be provided with necessary facilities and equipments to work with.

* **Social Acceptability:** for any occupation to worth calling, it must be socially acceptable, able to perform crucial socializing roles or functions in the society. This implies demonstration of a high degree of functional skills.

Emergence of Teacher education in Nigeria

The origin of teaching as a profession in the contemporary Nigerian setting will be incomplete without reference to its evolution in the traditional societies. Initially, teaching took place in the family. In this regards, i.e in the early societies, the culture of the people were "caught" by the younger generation through enculturation by participation, children learnt unconsciously while the elders taught them without being conscious. (Abimbola, 2004). This was the situation in the traditional societies within the Nigerian setting before the era of western. Christian missionaries that introduced western education.

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In this regards, Salami (2009) opined that the origin of formal teacher education is closely tied to the efforts of the early Christian missionaries, which was meant to protect their religious interests. This is so as they selected and trainees to become dual purpose personnel teachers in schools and catechist in the churches.

The church missionary society (CMS) established the first teacher training college in Abeokuta in 1859, it was moved to Lagos in 1867 and fused into CMS grammar school. By 1896, it was again moved to Oyo, on the advice of the first African Anglican Bishop Ajayi Crowther and named St Andrew's College. This later got converted to the present day Ajayi Crowther University Oyo (Salami 2009). In line with the foregoing, Sothern Baptist mission started a theological seminary in Ogbomoso in 1853, it was later changed to a Baptist College that incorporate teacher training courses into its curriculum in 1897. The college was shifted to Saki and finally to Iwo as a full teacher training College which later metamorphosed to the present day Bowen University, Iwo. The Roman catholic Mission (RCM) also ventured into the establishment of teacher training College, of which St. Gregory College, Ibadan (1876) and Mount Carmel College Ilorin are testimonials. The Methodist church established the Western College Ibadan as a teacher training College in 1905 while the Presbyterian established the Wadell College in 1807.

With the colonial administration intervention in educational affairs, teacher education in Nigeria got a boost. This came via educational ordinances of 1882, and 1897, which officially marked the beginning of government and mission via advisory and supervisory roles related to provision of guidelines that attracted government grants in- aids to schools.

The British Colonial administration gave official recognition to teaching as a profession, placed emphasis on the need for adequate training of

teachers and also enacted a code to grant-aid? All teacher training institutions for quality production of various grades of teachers.

The Phelps-Stokes Commission reports triggered off the establishment of departments of education in the north and south of Nigeria. It was the report that brought about the take-off of yaba Higher College in 1932 to offer a 3 year diploma in education. The programme was discontinued with the establishment of university College Ibadan on 18 January 1948, while the affected students were transferred to the University to be part of the (21 out of 104 students) pioneer under-graduates.

The Ashby Commission report recommendations of 1959 gave impetus to further the enhancement of teacher education in Nigeria. It was one of their recommendations that led to the introduction of a full degree programme in education, pioneered by the university of Nigeria, Nsukka in 1963 followed by Unibadan in 1963, ABU in 1964, OAU ife 1967 and Unilorin in 1975. The implementation of the need for non-graduate teachers by Ashby Commission led to the emergence of Advanced Teachers' Colleges/ Colleges of Education. They were initially meant to award grade I teacher certificate but later changed to Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE).

The inauguration of compulsory universal primary education in 1976 and the need to produce teachers to match the anticipated pupils enrolment of 9,511,000, the federal and state government established various teachers training colleges. Some were to train for one year pivotal programme for WASC holders, two years for WASC failed, three years for modern three holders, and five years for standard four and first school leaving certificate holders (Abimbola 2004).

In the same light, National Teachers institute (NTI) was set up in 1976 with the mandate to upgrade unqualified teachers, using the distance learning system. NTI was to achieve this objective through organizing seminar courses. It was this development that geared up ABU Zaria to start

the Teacher's in service educational programme (TISEP) with similar motives as the NTI. Also, many universities and colleges of education started sandwich degree and NCE sandwich programme to ensure greater access to education.

In 1989, the federal government set up the National commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) via decree No 31 (now Act 31 of the National assembly), with the mandate to design and develop curriculum monitor, accredit and provide minimum standard for operations in all colleges of education in Nigeria.

In a bid to enhance professional development, the federal government, after much pressure from education stakeholders established the Teachers Registration Council of Nigerian (TRCN) in 1993. The agency was to serve as a regulatory body on matters related to the teaching profession in the country.

Professionalism and Functional Teacher education in Nigeria

Having highlighted the concept of professionalism, its definitions and criteria and a brief history of teaching in Nigeria, we now proceed to an analyze how well entrenched the issue of professionalism of teaching on functional basis within the Nigeria's teacher education programme is.

Firstly, on the issue of training, it is to be noted that deliberate teacher education curriculum is put in place in Nigeria. As is it's succinctly highlighted in FRN (2004) section 8 (B) no 71, which spells out the goals of Teacher education and specifically listed institutions that are recognized to give required professional training to meet required standards. These institutions so recognized are colleges of education, faculties of education, institutes of education, National Teachers Institute, schools of education in polytechnics, National Institute for Nigerian languages and National mathematical centre. so recognized are colleges of education, faculties of education, institutes of

education, National Teachers Institute, schools of education in polytechnics, National Institute for Nigerian languages and National mathematical centre.

The aforementioned institutions offer various teacher training courses spanning various durations and complexities, more so, they are fully accredited to perform the roles of teacher trainers within the Nigerian context. These institutions offer pedagogical and academic courses to sufficiently prepare trainees for the tasks of teaching. Hence, trainees are functionally trained to perform their roles in the society.

As regards new entrants to the teaching profession, FRN (2004) has stated that the minimum qualification for entry into the teaching profession shall be the Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE). To ensure that graduates with this certificate have adequate exposure to the main elements of basic curriculum, the federal government set up the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) in 1989. The NCCE mandate, which among others, includes laying down minimum standards for all teacher education programmes and accrediting certificates has been pursued vigorously since inception to maintain functional teachers' education.

In line with its mandate, the TRCN determines who are teachers, determines what standards of knowledge and skills to be obtained by persons seeking to become registered teachers, maintains a register for all teachers, regulates and controls teaching profession in all ramifications and classify from time to time members of the teaching profession. (TRCN, 2008). The implication of the foregoing for would-be teachers is that they would henceforth undergo all those necessary intellectual, professions.

Another implication of TRCN mandate is that all who practice teaching jobs in Nigeria education system must be trained teachers registered and regulated by TRCN. Hence, no category of teachers is exempted from TRCN control; meaning all persons involved in teaching at both private and public establishments are bound by the act regulating teaching.

control; meaning all persons involved in teaching at both private and public establishments are bound by the act regulating teaching.

With respect to internship for this via teaching practice exercise. This is an integral part of teacher education, which socializes or exposes intending teachers into practicing the art of teaching. In view of its importance, the NCCE has made teaching practice six credit compulsory course unit to last for a period of twenty six duration to run at a stretch from mid- September to December, and January to April (i.e two terms).

In another dimension, FRN (2004) stipulates in section 8 subsections 78(b) that, "newly qualified teachers shall serve a period of internship one (1) year for degree holders and two (2) years for NCE holders. It is hoped that such period will further qualify intending teachers to be well adjusted to the teaching profession as such, they will be able to function maximally as professionals.

In the realm of remuneration for service rendered, teachers of various categories at various levels of education are not left out of approved government welfare packages. It is to be noted that teachers at the primary and secondary schools in Nigeria now enjoy the teachers salary scale, whereas at the tertiary institutions, teachers are paid consolidated salary scales which put them at par with their civil servant counterparts.

To enhance functionality in teacher education, FRN (2004) section 8, subsections 74-76 emphasize continuous exposure of teachers to changes in methodology, and innovations in curriculum. It opined that in service training shall be developed as an integral part of continuing teacher education so as to cater for inadequacies. It also pointed out that opportunities will be created for professional growth at all levels. In view of the above, TRCN, (2008) opined that it shall establish minimum standards for and execution of mandatory continuing professional development as to ensure all teachers are kept abreast of development in the theory and practice of the profession.

Constraints to functional teacher Education in Nigeria

A critical look at the goals of teacher education spelt out under section 8, subsection 7 (a-e) in the FRN (2004) vis- vis the issue of functionality in teacher education will stir one's emotion to ask:

- * Are teacher trainees highly motivated, conscientious, and efficient?
- * Can we say trainee have the enquiry and creative spirits?
- * Can we say they have adequate intellectual and professional training with concomitant commitment to the teaching profession?

It is most likely that answers to the foregoing will be uncomplimentary to the profession. Taken cognizance of practices of standard control in other profession on comparative basis to quality control in teachers education, functionality practices will drive home this point. For example, the entry requirements for professions such as medicine, pharmacy, law, and engineering e.t.c are incomparable to that of the teaching profession as large number of untrained and unqualified personnels are involved in teaching today. What about programme duration =how many years do law, medicine, pharmacy, engineering students spend to complete their programme as compared to that of education students? In the realm of exposure to practicum, we ask how many months/ years do medical, law and pharmacy undergraduates spend compared to the recently introduced 26 weeks of teaching practice?.

On the issue of internship though expressly stated "one year for degree holders and two years for NCE holders" (FRN, 2004), this phrase only appears as an innovation only on paper, and not in practice in any part of the country, without which in other profession no one can practice or function. A critical examination of internship programmes of other professions reveals intensity, rigor, academic intellectualism, and vibrancy which all undergraduates partake in with all seriousness, irrespective of drills faced. When compared side by side with teaching practice it is seen as merely "more exercise in

futility" (Ciwar, 2005). side by side with teaching practice it is seen as merely "more exercise in futility" (Ciwar, 2005).

In another dimension, section 8 subsection 70 © of FRN (2004) makes NCE to be the minimum entry qualification of the teaching profession. Yet, we have an army of untrained and unqualified personnel in teaching. As at 2006, NTI reported that there still exists over 70,000 untrained and unqualified teachers in the Nigeria public school (TRCN 2008).

Recommendations

Functional teacher education is imperative to enhancing national development, as no nation can rise above the quality of its teachers. This is in line with the general consensus that teachers are the main determinants of the quality of education and that all education systems depend very much on the competence, commitment and motivation of the teachers. (NERDC, 1980).

To ensure qualitative, functional teacher education for Nigeria, we hereby recommend that the following steps be taken:-

- * The national Commission for Colleges of Education as a supervisory body for teacher production should liase with
- * the Joint Admissions and matriculation Board so as to introduce attitude and personality component tests as well as oral interview for selection of prospective students teachers.
- * Teachers registration council of Nigeria (TRCN) that was set up to regulate the teaching profession should be adequately involved in the supervision of instructions and examinations leading to the approval of qualification for teachers in the country.
- * The National teacher institute (NTI), Teachers registration council of Nigeria (TRCN), national university commission (NUC), National

Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE), and National Business technical education Board (NABTEB) should collaborate as sister agencies to further ensure quality assurance in teacher education.

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* To ensure that teaching attains true professional status, everyone performing teaching roles across the length and breath of the country should be compelled to register and all recalcitrant ones especially in polytechnics and universities be made to undergo teaching professional courses or shown the way out of profession.

* Trainee teachers should be dully informed "that newly qualified teachers shall serves a period of internship one (1) year for degree holders and two (2) years for NCE holders" (FRN, 2004). It is expedient on the part of government to clarify this issue, spell out its modalities and adequately finance it.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this paper up does not claim exhaustive treatment of the topic but it is an attempt that x-rays some training errors, highlighting areas for changes, with some recommendations. Finally, let every one in the teaching profession work together as a team in cultivating the garden of teaching and say "those who have nothing to do with thorns must never attempt to gather flowers." In other words, every one in the teaching profession must guide the profession jealously upholding the integrity of the teaching profession like other noble professions so that there will be no room for those who want to make the profession a stepping stone to lucrative jobs.

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